

**TWENTY-THIRD
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CONDUCTIVE SMART NANOCOMPOSITE MATERIALS FOR STRUCTURAL HEALTH MONITORING AND STRAIN DETECTION

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SMART MATERIALS

CONDUCTIVE SMART NANOCOMPOSITE MATERIALS FOR STRUCTURAL HEALTH MONITORING AND MOTION DETECTION

Main type of sensors for SHM

The most common methods for SHM consist of integrating, inside or on the surface of the structure to be monitored, devices that measure changes in different physical parameters due to the appearance of structural damage or mechanical deformations.

- Passive acoustic sensors. Measures changes in strain
- Strain gauges. Measures changes in conductivity (from the gauge)
- Accelerometers. Measure accelerations.
- Fiber optic sensors. Measures reflected optical signals
- Ultrasonic sensors. Measures reflected ultrasonic signals

DISADVANTAGES

- *Fragile*
- *Difficulty seeing through several inches of the structure*
- *Placement near the place where the damage occurs (which is not known a priori)*
- *Interpreting the signals can be difficult*
- *Prone to long-term failure*
- *They are disturbed by environmental noise*
- *Lack of sensitivity to detect microcracks*
- *High cost*

↓ ↓ ↓ ↓
Alternative plan

The *smart materials* that allow applications in both SHM and strain detection are the same: Conductive polymeric nanocomposites.
Integrating carbon based Nanomaterials (CNTs, graphene, carbon black...).

Piezoresistivity is defined as the coupling phenomenon between a mechanical stimulus (strain, ϵ) and a change in electrical resistance (ΔR , where R is the electrical resistance)

- When piezoresistive materials are stretched by an external force, the material resistance varies to a certain extent.

STRAIN detection

- When firmly attached to a deformable object, piezoresistive elements stretch as the object experiences strain, resulting in variable resistance.

Structural Health Monitoring: Conductivity change Method $\Delta\sigma$

$$\sigma = 1/\rho = 1/R * 0,02 \text{ (S/m)}$$

Resistivity change corresponding to rubber filled with CNT when manually fold and unfold (AIMEN graph, not the picture)

Commercial Conductive 3D Filaments: Thermoplastic Polymer + Carbon-Based Nanoadditives

Coupon	Description	Resistance
PLA	Carbon Black (20%)	0,588E3 ohm
ESD safe ABS	Unknown load of MWCNTs	0,464E6 ohm
CNT PETG	Unknown load of CNTs	0,346E9 ohm
PEKK-ESD	Unknown load of CNTs	48.5E6 ohm

All materials show a gradual change (decrease in conductivity) with increasing defect size: they could be proposed for SHM.

Conductivity change Method $\Delta\sigma$
 $\sigma = 1/\rho = 1/R * 0,02$ (S/m)

Sánchez-Sobrado #1 et al.
Functional Composite Materials (2023) 4:2
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Functional Composite Materials

RESEARCH Open Access

Evaluation of conductive smart composite polymeric materials for potential applications in structural health monitoring and strain detection

Olalla Sánchez-Sobrado*, Daniel Rodríguez, Ricardo Losada and Elena Rodríguez

Simultaneous measurements of mechanical deformation and electrical conductivity during a tensile test, using acquisition equipment.

- For all materials, the resistivity increases during deformation, and as soon as the deformation ceases and the material returns to its original state, the resistivity also decreases.
- When polymers reach their breaking point, the resistivity curve collapses

Sanchez-Sobrado et al. Functional Composite Materials (2023) 4:2
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Functional Composite Materials

RESEARCH

Open Access

Evaluation of conductive smart composite polymeric materials for potential applications in structural health monitoring and strain detection

Olalla Sanchez-Sobrado*, Daniel Rodriguez, Ricardo Losada and Elena Rodriguez

PEEK based 3D printing filament including *CNTs* and *graphene*

Polymers **2018**, 10, 925; doi:10.3390/polym10080925

CONDUCTIVE SMART NANOCOMPOSITE MATERIALS FOR STRUCTURAL HEALTH MONITORING AND MOTION DETECTION

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Epoxy resin + CNTs

Evolution of change of the resistivity with defect size

Simultaneous measurements of resistivity change (red lines) and strain (blue lines) for conductive epoxy resin

Rubber+ CNTs

- Resistivity increases during deformation, and as soon as the deformation ceases and the material returns to its original state, the resistivity also decreases.
- Material shows a gradual change (decrease in conductivity) with increasing defect size: it could be proposed for SHM

CNT fibres

Continuous CNT fibres :

- Exhibit piezoresistive behaviour
- Are easily embeddable in composites

A grid on sensors allows to monitor strain and to relate its changes to the mechanical properties of the laminate panel

SEM image of the densified CNT fibre

CNT fibres as embedded strain sensors

Scheme of the arrangement of a grid of embedded CNTs fibre sensors in a rectangular panel

Zarzoso, M., Mikhalchan, A., Vilatela, J.J. and Gonzalez, C.
Carbon nanotube fibre-based sensors for strain monitoring of CF/PAEK composites (In preparation)

3D printed filaments with continuous CNT fibres

dry cCNT fibre

3D printed cCNT fibre

CNT fibres as embedded strain sensors

Zarzo, M., Mikhalchan, A., Vilatela, J.J. and Gonzalez, C.
Carbon nanotube fibre-based sensors for strain monitoring of CF/PAEK composites (In preparation)

CONCLUSIONS

- In the presented work, electrical properties, and both damage and strain dependent electrical resistance characteristics of several different carbon-based/polymer composite and nanocomposite materials were investigated: (a) CNTs reinforced RTM6 Epoxy resin, (b) different carbon-based nano additives thermoplastic composite for 3D printing technologies prepreg composite: PLA/CB; ABS/CNTs; PETG/CNTs and PEKK/CNTs and (c) long carbon fiber composite laminates.
- All polymeric conductive composite and nanocomposite materials evaluated in this work present response to the formation of structural damage, being nanocomposite based in small amount of nanomaterials like CNTs the most sensitive and promised for applications in SHM.
- All polymeric conductive composite and nanocomposite materials evaluated of different nature (thermoset and thermoplastic) have been proved suitable for applications in strain and motion detection. Long carbon fiber-based composites, allow to detect the production of microcracks during tensile tests.

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Thanks for your attention

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